

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL COMMUNICATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract. *The phenomenon of social communication occurs, first of all, with direct communication of people in small groups. Specific phenomena of this type of communication include: a set of positions of group members on obtaining and storing important information for the group (the structure of communication flows); group influence and the degree of identification of the individual with the group; group decision-making; formation of consent, the formation of a special culture of the group. In the development of society, opinions and reflections on the importance of social communication are kept.*

Keywords: *society, social, communication, progress, norm, communication, speech, communication, audience.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ КОММУНИКАЦИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ОБЩЕСТВА

Аннотация. *Феномен социальной коммуникации возникает, прежде всего, при непосредственном общении людей в малых группах. К специфическим явлениям этого вида общения относятся: совокупность позиций членов группы по получению и хранению важной для группы информации (структура коммуникативных потоков); влияние группы и степень идентификации личности с группой; групповое принятие решений; формирование согласия, формирование особой культуры группы. В развитии общества сохраняются мнения и размышления о важности социальной коммуникации.*

Ключевые слова: *общество, социальное, общение, прогресс, норма, общение, речь, общение, аудитория.*

INTRODUCTION

The lexical consistency of group communication, along with the standards and guidelines for appropriate communication strategies, are distinguishing characteristics. Some academics mention the impact of new information transmission technologies while taking into account the idea of "Mass Communication," keeping in mind this "narrow" component of communicative engagement. for a sizable or modest audience. By means of symbols and symbols, it is transferred. Technology has evolved quickly and taken on many different shapes, but this does not necessarily indicate that it is any more effective. Additionally, according to some theories, this phenomenon can be used to influence sizable audiences, thereby achieving the objectives of those who broadcast information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Without these five components, the communication process cannot be carried out:

1. Communicator - the one who begins the transmission and forms it in the form of speech, text, audio and video;
2. The message itself;
3. Channel where communication with viewers is established;
4. Information-oriented audience;
5. The purpose of the transmission and the degree of responsiveness of the message (impact).

This, social communication is characterized by the presence of certain information distributed through a wide audience, the purpose of which is to influence the behavior, feelings and emotions of people. In addition, there is only a presentation of information aimed at intellectual development public and expanding their worldview. Such a presentation is characterized by neutrality and maximum possible objectivity without elements of assessment. Some researchers understand social communication not only as a large-scale distribution of the message, but also as an individual exchange that takes place between two people. Its usual form is conversation. Although it corresponds to the definition of "social", it is often used in this sense when it comes to a group or a mass of people. Therefore, in this article we will use a common meaning. According to the type of audience, social communication is divided into specialized and public. The second category does not represent any originality and is ready to perceive any socially significant information. According to the source of the message, it can be both formal and informal: official statements of the authorities coincide with the first type, and, for example, rumors about the stars belong to the second. It can be both verbal and non-verbal through the delivery channel. Intention is purpose. A very important element, because the quality of perception depends on it. In modern communication, there are several types of intentions:

1. Dissemination of knowledge about the environment, awareness of people;
2. Popularization of the ideas of goodness, attracting the attention of the audience to the dissemination of culture and reliable information about it;
3. Impact on public opinion and consciousness, as well as on the audience;
4. Help and support in solving difficult problems, identifying situations;
5. Striving for neutral and pseudoobjective coverage of phenomena;
6. Establishing a dialogue between the audience and the broadcast source.

RESULTS

The establishment of contact between the addressee and the recipient is the cornerstone of any sort of communication. It is not required to discuss communication effectiveness if it is inadequately established or if the recipient of the information interprets the information incorrectly. As a result, this subject is crucial for discussing all forms of communication. The following parameters can be used to gauge this phenomenon's effectiveness:

1. The communicator's desire to make it apparent to the audience why he publishes information and why he broadcasts specific occurrences is a must.
2. The confidence test comes next. Communication can be successful if the audience has faith in the message's source and its delivery method. The author's objectives.

Messages should not be disturbed or presented in an overly neutral form: this spoils their naturalness and, therefore, binds to lies, reducing the effectiveness of the effect. Thus, this can be easily achieved if you adhere to a number of principles of Information Presentation and clearly demonstrate your attitude towards the audience. Although there are different types of communication, this article provides the most universal features and tips that will be useful to everyone who is engaged in SMS. Remember that the most important component of social interaction will be social communication. Although in some cases it is possible to interact without communication, in most cases social contacts involve communication.

Communication-mutual exchange of information, which means that both participants are directed towards mutual openness of the partner. Such an exchange occurs not necessarily in oral form (verbal), but also in non-verbal form. Non-verbal communication is much older than verbal

communication. It should be noted that it contains gestures and facial expressions, dance, music, Fine Arts, Sculpture and architecture. In fact, engineering structures, temples, palaces, sculptures and Paintings left over from past centuries provide unconditional information about the life, feelings, relationships of people who have long died. The essence of the communication process, as follows from the definition, is to transfer the message containing the information to another participant. In sociology, the process of communication is called the action of revealing the content of its consciousness.

But a signal isn't always a message or an alert. For instance, if a stranger approaches us on the street and speaks to us in a language we do not understand, we receive such a signal but no actual message. Of course, no communication nor gathering of information takes place in this scenario. If something that we already know is mentioned, we will hear it, but it won't be knowledge that we need to know. Only if the communication contains anything we don't know will it be information. Since communication is by its very nature a symbolic process, specific carriers—signs and symbols—are required for the transmission of information during the communicative process. Objects that reveal their hidden significance serve society as symbols rather than as things in and of themselves.

DISCUSSION

Signs are words, gestures, postures, facial expressions, sometimes expressive behavior (laughter, smile, tears, sigh, etc.). Language is the most important system of signs institutionalized by society and, therefore, of a historical nature. The individual is born and formed in a certain social context, where the specific structure of the language is already established. Hence, the language of any society indirectly indicates the structure of society and, as it were, determines the specifics of social communication. Do not forget that an important feature of any communication process will be the intention of the participants to influence each other. Such mechanisms can be influenced by psychological effects:

1. persuasion is a process of targeted communicative influence, characterized by the logical justification of a message (or several messages) in order to achieve the consent of the interlocutor (or audience) to the expressed point of view;
2. suggestion is a method of communicative influence designed for the critical perception of information; such a nature of perception does not require any detailed logical analysis, assessment or deep reflection, but is carried out by influencing feelings, emotions, which, in turn, affects the intellectual and volitional characteristics of a person unaware of being exposed to external influences. affects.

It is enough to highlight such a phenomenon as ethnic stereotype, which is characterized by assessment, emotional coloring and bias. The indicative space of an ethnic stereotype is formed by: ethnic characteristics, character traits, language, assessment of the behavior and dynamic characteristics of a person, qualities that determine the attitude towards people, etc. Interethnic communication contributes to the transfer of culture and social forms. experience. At the interpersonal level, subjective 7 interactions occur, in which the subjective world of one person opens up to another. At the same time, the individual acts as a carrier of self-awareness and culture of the ethnic group.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the proposal is used to create a state in which the interlocutor pushes him to certain actions. The effectiveness of the communication process directly depends on the

individual characteristics of the individual, the level of his education, culture, State of mind and level of influence. Excluding the above, the power of impact largely depends on the visibility, accessibility, imagery and compactness of the data. The effectiveness of communicative means is largely determined by how the content of the proposed message, in general, responds to the interests and needs of the audience. All these aspects of relations in society are clearly manifested in interethnic relations and communication and are manifested in the phenomena of interethnic perception.

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